

WAERMER Waermewende im urbanen Gebäudebestand mit Hilfe interaktiver Entscheidungsraumanalyse

**Never change a running system? What hinders
homeowners from replacing their fossil-based heating
systems with more environmentally friendly ones**

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Overview

1. Introduction

In order to reduce human-caused CO₂ emissions, the private heating sector must be transformed, shifting from fossil energy sources to more environmentally friendly alternatives. As shown in our broad survey study (Holzberg & Ernst, 2025), German homeowners are primarily focused on financial and construction-related factors (perceived behavior control) when considering changing a fossil-based heating system to a heating system that relies on renewable energy sources. To gain insights into the specific and individual situations of homeowners, a semi-structured interview study was conducted in 2025. The goal of this study is to explore in detail the current heating systems of homeowners, how they perceive these systems, as well as their perceptions of certain heating systems, and the potential reasons and barriers for changing their system.

2. Sample recruitment and description

Participants who took part in our broad survey study (see Deliverable 2.5) were additionally asked whether they would be interested in participating in a further study. All homeowners who expressed interest were contacted again and invited to take part in an interview. Of the 43 homeowners contacted, 20 interviews were conducted. Two interviews were excluded from the final sample because it was not possible to distinguish between their own home situation and their role as a landlord, or because they did not live in their own home. One interview was excluded due to poor audio quality, making transcription impossible. The final sample consists of 17 interviews. Of these, two participants did not wish to state their gender, five identified as female, and ten as male. Three participants declined to share their age. The remaining 14 participants had a mean age of 58, with the youngest being 30 and the eldest 73. All participants were homeowners who also live in their own homes. Data collection took place from 23 January 2025 to 28 April 2025. The duration of the interviews ranged from 20 minutes to 1 hour and 15 minutes.

3. Methods

For the interview, a semi-structured interview guide was developed and pre-tested. Depending on the situation, some questions were asked or omitted (tailored testing). A semi-structured approach means that key questions are formulated and intended to be covered but can be adapted to the context. If the interviewer wishes to explore an additional topic, this is also possible. The interviews were conducted either in person in the subjects' home in the city of Kiel or via Zoom.

3.1. Materials

The interview manual consists of 13 main questions, which were adapted as needed depending on the situation. To view the original interview manual in German, see Appendix 1. The initial questions are designed to depict the homeowner's current situation and their level of satisfaction with it. The first question is therefore: "What type of heating system do you currently use to heat your home?" followed by: "How old is the system?" Additionally, participants were asked whether they have a photovoltaic or solar thermal system. They were also asked whether they are satisfied with their current heating system and, if not, the reasons for their dissatisfaction. Following these broader questions, more specific questions were asked: "Are you currently satisfied with its climate friendliness?"

After the current state of the heating situation has been identified, the participant is asked about possible changes to their current system: “Have you already thought about modernizing your heating system?” If the answer is yes, the follow-up question is: “What motivated you to take this step?” If the answer is no, the question is: “What would make you consider modernizing your heating system?” If the participant has already modernized their system a few years ago, these questions are adapted to refer to that time point. Depending on the situation, it is additionally asked whether the participant still considers changing their heating system now.

The next thematic section of the interview guide focuses on all possible heating systems that the participant has considered or thought about: “Which systems have you considered so far?” For each system mentioned, the participant is asked to identify the perceived pros and cons. Additional questions include: “Have you discussed this topic with others? Are there any other sources you have used to gather information?”; “Are there heating systems you would favor or exclude due to climate protection reasons?”; and “Why have you so far decided against this system, or what is currently preventing you from choosing it?”

The financial, informational, and political contexts were also addressed: “So far, heating systems based on renewable energy are significantly more expensive to purchase and install than gas or oil heating systems. How do you stand on this issue regarding such renewable heating systems?”; “Do you feel sufficiently informed about funding opportunities for the systems? (What is missing for you?)” and “How do you perceive the support provided by the government?”.

If the topic of heat pumps or heating grid did not arise during the discussion of specific systems, the following questions were asked additionally: “Imagine that in your neighborhood, it became possible to connect to a local or district heating grid. Would you consider connecting to such a network?” and “What do you generally think of heat pumps?”

To assess whether the topic has been discussed with professionals, the following question was asked: “Have you already had experience with an energy consultant or with heating installers?” If yes, further questions were asked regarding satisfaction with these professionals and whether their recommendations were taken into account.

Two questions were included to specifically address potential barriers to change: “Are you currently hesitating to take individual action because you are waiting to see how the local heat planning for your neighborhood will turn out?” and “Do you feel that you would like more information before you can proceed with a heating system renovation? (What kind of information would you like to have? From whom should that information come?)”

The final two questions were: “After the completion of the communal heating planning, heating systems must be supplied with at least 65% renewable energy sources when replaced. Have you already thought about how you would implement this requirement in such a case?” (if not already mentioned), and “Do you have any other aspects that are particularly important to you in connection with heating systems, which you feel have not yet been addressed and should be discussed?” — to identify any topics that may have been overlooked during the interview.

3.2. Analysis

The Interviews were locally transcribed using Whisper (OpenAI, 2023). For the analysis of the qualitative data, the software MAXQDA (version 24.1.0; VERBI Software GmbH, 2024) was used. To analyze the transcribed interviews, the coding process and categories were developed in accordance with content analysis and inductive categorization as proposed by Mayring (2022). Figure 1 illustrates the development of the code system.

Initially, the broad thematic sections of the interviews were used as a reference to inductively develop and refine the categories, based on pilot interviews. Using this initial code system, the first 10 interviews were analyzed, during which the code system was further adapted. The revised code system was then applied to the next 10 interviews. During this phase, three interviews were excluded. Minor adjustments were made to the category system.

Figure 1: Data analysis process in accordance with Mayring (2022).

The final sample of 17 interviews was then re-analyzed using the third version of the code system, after which no further changes were made to the code system.

The main categories for analysis include:

- **Current heating system**, including whether it is based on fossil or renewable energy sources, its age, and the presence of additional systems such as photovoltaic (PV) or solar thermal systems, as well as reasons for past changes (if the current system has been replaced). This category also captures the satisfaction of the participant with the system.
- **Reasons for or against a potential change**, encompassing not only positive and negative aspects but also neutral considerations mentioned by participants.
- **Possible heating systems**, detailing the positive, negative, and neutral aspects associated with specific systems.
- **Current barriers**, collecting all factors that hinder homeowners from replacing their heating systems.

- **Rejecting/preferring a system**, capturing general attitudes toward specific systems, including preferences or rejections.
- **Information and knowledge sources**
- **Finances and subsidies**

4. Results

In the following sections, the statements of participants regarding the described topic sections are presented.

4.1. Current heating system

Of the 17 households interviewed, the current heating system is based on gas in 13 cases. Two households use an air-to-water heat pump, one is connected to a district heating grid, and one uses a wood gasification boiler.

The age of the gas heating systems ranges from 1 to 30 years. Two systems were installed in the past two years, three are between 6 and 10 years old, and one each is 15 and 17 years old. Five systems are between 20 and 25 years old, and one is 30 years old.

Thirteen households have additional energy systems. All households with renewable heating systems have either a PV, a balcony photovoltaic system or a solar thermal system. Of the households with fossil-based heating systems, nine have an additional heating system, which in most cases is a PV system or a balcony photovoltaic system.

Among the households with fossil fuel-based systems, four have no additional PV or solar thermal systems. One has a solar thermal system, and the other six have a PV system.

4.2. Satisfaction with current heating system

If we look at the households that already have renewable energy sources, all four stated they are satisfied with their system. One added that some renovations to the house are still needed, and another responded with a mixed answer: yes and no, because additional modifications are required.

Among the remaining thirteen households that use gas as their energy source, one stated they are very satisfied with their current system, and six reported being satisfied. One described the system as okay, while another said it does its job and is reliable and that he/she can't complain. One participant expressed satisfaction due to the system's convenience, though they noted it cannot remain this way indefinitely. Another said they are satisfied but would prefer a larger buffer tank. One answered that he/she is satisfied as it works but added that something else is desired, as the radiators are too hot.

Only one participant mentioned a desire for a renewable energy system specifically due to climate change. However, they also emphasized that they are satisfied with their current system and that it is functioning well at present.

In summary, only three households mentioned the possibility of changing their system when discussing satisfaction with their current setup. Only one explicitly referenced climate change and

renewable energy sources as a motivation for change. No participant reported being dissatisfied with the current system's performance.

The question about satisfaction was left open-ended and did not mention climate change or renewable energy sources at this stage, in order to avoid introducing bias or prompting socially desirable responses. For this reason, the question was later followed up with a specific inquiry: "Are you currently satisfied with the climate friendliness of your system?"

4.3. Satisfaction with its climate friendliness

Of the households already using renewable energy sources, three stated they are satisfied, while in one interview there was no direct response to the question.

Among the 13 households using gas as their energy source, four clearly answered "yes" to being satisfied. One participant stated they are satisfied as long as the chimney sweeper does not raise any concerns. A similar response was given by another participant, who expressed general satisfaction and noted that the chimney sweeper had confirmed the heating system's values were within acceptable limits, indicating that satisfaction is conditional on the system passing inspection.

Other responses included:

- As it emits CO₂ it can not be the perfect solution
- There could be more done regarding this topic
- Not being satisfied due to emission of CO₂

Two participants explicitly stated they are not satisfied with the climate friendliness of their system and believe this should be changed. One household linked their response to their overall energy consumption, stating they are not satisfied with it. They contextualized their consumption by comparing it to general statistics, noting that while their usage is low, they still wish it were even lower. Another participant did not clearly state whether they are satisfied with the climate friendliness of their system, saying that it is a gas boiler that emits CO₂. But that it would emit less than before.

4.4. Reasons for or against a change

The reasons provided by households that recently changed their heating system to a new gas system were primarily related to the age and condition of the previous system. One household mentioned that the old gas system was 16 years old and needed replacement. Another household, which had recently upgraded, cited climate change as a key motivation, specifically, the new gas system is more environmentally friendly than the previous one. However, financial constraints were a major factor: the household could not afford alternative systems and felt unable to secure a loan, especially given their age and financial situation. They expressed a desire to renovate their home, but the war in Ukraine led to rising costs across the board. Even with available subsidies, they felt financially unable to proceed.

Another participant, who replaced a gas system older than 20 years due to its failure, noted that the topic of heat pumps had not been discussed at that time (more than 5 years ago). Local counseling services also played a role in prompting the decision to consider a change.

Households that switched to renewable-based systems provided various motivations:

- One household wanted to no longer leave a footprint. The war in Ukraine, leading to reduced gas supplies and rising gas prices, was the key tipping point.
- Another household (also switching from gas) cited the need for repairs on the old system and anticipated future increases in gas prices.
- A household switching from a fossil-based system to a system with renewable energy resources emphasizes climate protection as a reason, particularly after purchasing their home.
- One household wanted to achieve greater energy autonomy and reduce heating costs.

Reasons for a general and potential change are summarized in Table 1. The motivations cited by homeowners for considering a change are diverse and varied. Most participants indicated that financial factors, in some form, play a role in their consideration of system change. These financial reasons themselves differ significantly.

One participant stated that a change would only be considered if the cost of not connecting to a heating grid would be higher. Another mentioned that the property value would increase if the home were connected to a district heating grid. The upcoming increase in CO₂ taxation was also mentioned as a future financial incentive to act. Three participants noted that subsidies play a significant role in their decision-making. Additionally, two participants mentioned that the discussion surrounding the new heating law created a sense of necessity, prompting them to consider a change.

Table 1: Reasons participants mentioned that prompted them to think about a heating system change

Reason for a possible change	Number of participants
More space if the gas boiler is changed by a connection to a heating grid	1
Goal to go away from fossil energy sources and climate concerns	5
Partly repair of old system and installer mentioned it could fail completely	2
Other people and information event	2
Energy crisis and war against the Ukraine	1
Finances	6
Necessity (law)	2
Autonomy/Autarky	1

Reasons against changing the heating system included financial constraints: one participant stated there is not enough money to make the change. Five households indicated they do not wish to change

their system as long as the current system is still functioning. One participant mentioned that heat pumps were not yet technologically ready to adequately heat their home.

4.5. Pros and cons of possible heating systems

Apart from the participants' current heating situation and whether they have considered a change, it was also explored which systems they could imagine installing or ruling out, as well as the pros and cons they perceive for different heating systems. The following section presents the identified pros and cons for each system.

Regarding the negative aspects, noise issues were mentioned with varying intensity. Some participants simply stated they find the systems too loud, while others described the noise as a health concern and a form of environmental pollution.

If we look at the neutral, positive, and negative aspects mentioned by participants regarding heat pumps, a wide variety of factors emerge (see Table 2). Interestingly, some aspects were mentioned in both positive and negative categories. For example, electricity generated by a photovoltaic (PV) system was cited as a positive factor yet also raised as a concern, likely due to issues related to storage, grid integration or the availability of power in winter. Similarly, noise was mentioned across all three categories, highlighting its dual perception as both a drawback and, in some cases, a manageable trade-off for other benefits.

In Table 3, the pros and cons of a district heating grid are presented. It can be seen that more positive aspects were mentioned in terms of frequency. A neutral and negative factor mentioned was the time aspect: participants noted that the decision-making process regarding whether a network will be established, and the timeline for its availability and connection, takes too long.

Four participants highlighted a positive aspect of district heating: the fact that they would not need to manage or maintain the system themselves. On the other hand, six households mentioned dependence on the supplier as a negative aspect.

Another heating system mentioned is a pellet or wood-fired system (see Table 4). For pellet systems, negative aspects were mentioned more frequently than positive ones. A key concern was the lack of space available for storing pellets. Other issues raised, ranging from expressions of concern to factual statements, include the sustainability of pellet systems compared to fossil-based systems (see Table 4).

Positive aspects mentioned include the ability to choose the origin of the pellets and control their cost, as well as a better CO₂ balance when the wood is sourced regionally.

Table 2: Neutral, positive and negative aspects that were mentioned by participants regarding the heating system heat pump

Heat pump		
Neutral aspects	Positive aspects	Negative aspects
Noise of the system (2)	Based on electricity that can be produced through PV system (2)	Thought about a ground-source heat pump but because of the boreholes it is not an option; boreholes are too costly (2)
Air-to-air heat pump can be segmented (considering installation)	Family members use one and it works well.	Air-to-air heat pump: there is a constant airflow
Has to be somewhere (space)	Climate friendliness (2)	Not an option due to high costs (2) (especially compared to a gas system), unnatural high costs
Unsure about new technologies	Now the technology has gotten better (2) (the supply water temperature can be lower and the noise level reduced (3))	Would not be energy efficient
Not sure how the system works	One can still get subsidies	Not aesthetic in front of the house (2)
Would the electricity network withstand if so many people use a heat pump	It makes sense to utilize heat from the environment	High need of electricity in winter that cannot be provided by own PV system (3)
	In summer warm water can be provided as well	Renovations would be needed
	Ground-source heat pump is more efficient than other systems	Noise concerns (4): being too loud if more people have them, noise as annoying and affecting health, noise as pollution
	Other countries use this since years	The power grid would not be able to withstand

Heat pump		
Neutral aspects	Positive aspects	Negative aspects
	Air-to-air heat pump can be used to cool down in summer	
	It provides clean energy	

Note: The number in parentheses shows how many different participants mentioned the aspect. If there is no number in parentheses it was mentioned by one participant.

Table 3: Neutral, positive and negative aspects that were mentioned by participants regarding a heating grid

Heating grid		
Neutral aspects	Positive aspects	Negative aspects
It would have been an option if it had already existed or if it had been built quickly. (2)	Local heating grid with the river nearby. It would have the positive effect of cooling down the water. An energy consultant mentioned that as a best recommendation	It takes a long time until it is ready to get connected (4)
If a company owns it, one is dependent on their pricing structure (mentioned as a con, but would not state it as such)	It is low maintenance / one does not have to do it by oneself (5)	A lot of uncertainties like, are there enough people who would connect their houses, uncertainty and dependence to the provider
It may be cheaper, not sure. At least cheaper than now (gas)	Secure supply	One is dependent on a supplier (6)

Heating grid		
Neutral aspects	Positive aspects	Negative aspects
	Technically innovative	High transmission loss
	Just a heat exchanger, no system installed in front of the house (heat pump)	Unrealistic due to the specific conditions of the house
	Sounds promising	If it is not more ecological than a heat pump
	The problem is solved: finding an ecologically sensible and future-proof heating system. One does not have to think about it	Installation costs
	Like the idea that not everyone has their own system, but a shared one /joint use (2)	Installation itself (construction works)
	Clean energy /climate friendly (3)	
	No first primary purchase	
	Not as expensive	

Note: The number in parentheses shows how many different participants mentioned the aspect. If there is no number in parentheses it was mentioned by one participant.

Table 4: Neutral, positive and negative aspects that were mentioned by participants regarding a pellet heating system

Pellet heating system or firewood		
Neutral aspects	Positive aspects	Negative aspects
Not sure about pellets. Not enough knowledge about that system.	<p>One can decide oneself where the pellets are bought from and how much they cost</p> <p>Good CO₂ balance, if it is grown locally</p>	<p>Not sure if it's sustainable — still a raw material being burned.</p> <p>Where are the pellets from?</p> <p>Produce more emissions than with a good gas heating system</p> <p>Not a good place to store the pellets (5)</p> <p>Wood is a finite resource (2), there is not enough to provide everyone (1)</p> <p>Not possible due to required construction works</p> <p>Price fluctuations, dependent on those (2), dependent on pellets (2)</p> <p>Many different information (particulate matter)</p> <p>Those systems need many repairs</p> <p>Who guarantees that the wood is indeed regrown? (Greenwashing)</p> <p>Emissions from wood (1), it is a fossil energy source again (1), Not an alternative to a gas system (emissions again) (1)</p> <p>Leads to particulate matter (firewood (1) and pellet (1))</p>

Note: The number in parentheses shows how many different participants mentioned the aspect. If there is no number in parentheses it was mentioned by one participant.

Throughout the interviews, and in response to questions about systems that were considered, pros and cons of gas heating systems were mentioned. Negative aspects include rising gas prices (mentioned twice) and the fact that gas is a fossil fuel.

On the positive side, participants noted that gas systems are easy to operate and provide a sense of energy autonomy (autarky). Concerns were also expressed regarding the long-term availability of the gas grid, as well as uncertainty about future price developments and the potential for continued increases.

4.6. Current barriers

The current barriers that homeowners mentioned hindering them from changing their system at this time include age, specifically, feeling too old, combined with the difficulty that the investment may not amortize (1 participant). When asked what is currently preventing a change, one participant responded that they are in a state of conflict (in a dilemma). The political party that may be part of the government leads to uncertainty regarding future subsidies for renewable energy systems.

One participant mentioned that they have contacted an energy consultant, but the consultation is delayed, and they are choosing to wait for it. Three participants stated that the current system is still functioning, and therefore they do not see a need to change it. One participant cited a neighbor's heat pump as a concern, noting that the unit is relatively loud.

Six participants explicitly named finances as a barrier. It was also mentioned that there is a lack of time to properly inform oneself about the topic, as doing so requires too much effort in daily life. Additionally, six participants indicated throughout the interview that they are waiting for the decision whether a heating grid will be established, before considering an individual solution.

4.7. Preferred or rejected systems

Regarding the question about which systems would be preferred or rejected due to climate protection reasons, the responses can also be categorized into three groups: preference, rejection, and neutrality or uncertainty (Table 5). Rejected systems were those that use fossil energy sources as well as pellet systems. In one interview the question was asked if there would be systems that the participant would reject when considering a change (without the focus on climate protection reasons). The answer were heat pumps and PV system due to the noise level of a heat pump and the question where the cable for the PV system would be installed.

Table 5: Answers of participants to the question “Are there any heating systems you would reject or prefer due to climate protection reasons?”

neutral	preferring	Rejecting
Not sure about pellets	Photovoltaic systems. We would like to install a solar thermal system	Gas or oil (3), coal
Not really climate protection reasons. Somewhere	A local heating grid. It would be most effective if energy were produced on a large	No fossil sources. Pellets aren't ideal either, they are still a fossil fuel. And geothermal

neutral	preferring	Rejecting
everything must be produced. We need mixed systems.	scale. And then one wouldn't have to worry about the topic anymore. Solar thermal systems and heat pumps. Solar thermal systems are unfortunately not effective in winter. Heat pumps seem to be the most reasonable option. New technologies will certainly be developed, but I'm not entirely sure yet.	energy would be too demanding, both financially and in terms of construction. If we start to change our system, we do not want to use fossil energy sources. (2)
		Pellets (2)

Note: The number in parentheses shows how many different participants mentioned the aspect. If there is no number in parentheses it was mentioned by one participant.

4.8. Information sources

When examining homeowners' perceptions of their level of information, a wide range of opinions emerge. One participant stated they do not feel informed but also admitted they have not actively engaged in the topic. Another is actively seeking information, while two others indicated they are waiting for an energy consultation. One participant said they are unsure about their preferred system and are waiting for professional advice, although they feel relatively well-informed about subsidies. Three homeowners reported that they do not feel the need for additional information, and one acknowledged that subsidies are a complex topic but stated they have managed to navigate it independently.

Regarding information sources, eight participants mentioned using digital media such as the internet to gather information, and two additionally cited printed materials.

On the topic of heat pump noise, three participants shared personal observations from walking through their neighborhood. Two stated they do not perceive heat pumps as loud, while one mentioned they can hear them.

Homeowners also exchange information with neighbors, friends, family, and colleagues—resulting in a mix of positive and negative experiences.

On the professional side, two participants consulted their chimney sweeper. One noted that district heating grid involve dependence on the supplier and the inability to switch providers, while the other reported that the chimney sweeper was open to alternative heating systems. One participant mentioned that their architect advised against installing a heat pump due to the lack of suitable radiators or floor heating.

Four participants reported obtaining information directly from companies—through their websites, by requesting printed materials, or through company representatives. Information workshops organized by the city were mentioned by four participants, along with one who consulted an electrician and one who spoke with a heating installer.

If we take a closer look at what information participants received from their heating installer (HI), it is again a wide range of statements:

- Heat pumps nowadays are really good
- HI said he is not an expert with heat pumps, but with gas boiler systems
- Participant stated that a heat pump is not an option because the HI said they cost 40,000 euro which would be a lot and gas system would only cost a quarter
- Heat pumps were not that big at the time. Counselling for a wood-based system
- Regarding solar thermal system, the HI said it would not function because there is not enough space for storage.
- HI said that their company mainly installs heat pumps now, nearly no gas systems anymore
- The participant did not have a real talk about the topic. HI only mentioned that their heating system will not last forever
- Every time the HI is there, he says everything is fine. Therefore, they do not talk about that topic further
- The HI made the best solution for the situation and that it (gas system) can be adapted to hydrogen
- Regarding a solar thermal system: HI said one could get subsidies through the city
- HI said, if your system is still running “stay calm”

So, there is a wide variety of installers: Some appear to lack knowledge about newer systems, while others actively advise homeowners on renewable energy systems, or take into account the specific circumstances of each household, such as financial situation and the existing conditions of the property.

Next to the heating installer, some participants were asked if they had talked to an energy consultant. Below are some statements of the participants regarding an energy consultation. It is mentioned that the financial burden of recommended measures was not manageable, or that the heating system itself was not the focus of the consultation:

- Said it would be very complex, including high costs if a heat pump is wanted
- Had a consultation for renovations, not heating system
- Consultation was 10 years ago, it was not a topic back then
- Had one regarding insulation of the house. It was helpful, but because of the high prices it was not manageable
- We won a consultation through the community center. It was nice and informative how to become CO₂ neutral but because of the finances it is not doable. We did only smaller things regarding renovations (windows). We are very happy with that
- We recently had a consultation (through community center). Not that satisfying because of a lack of professional competence. It did not bring up something new
- Architect was the energy consultant (18 years ago). We want to make a new one in the future

4.9. Finances and subsidies

During the interviews, it was directly asked how participants viewed the financial aspects of renewable heating systems. Next to those direct answers, throughout the interview participants also mentioned financial aspects. Those viewpoints of the participants will be presented in the following section. In the following, the answers of participants are paraphrased. As the different answers of homeowners show, the variety of whether sustainable heating systems are seen as manageable financially ranges from participants stating they are not being able to provide enough money to participants who say that the finances are not a problem.

- Mentioned not being young anymore and not having that much money. Said he/she would not get that high loan anymore and somehow one would have to pay that back.
- Financially it would be manageable. Participant would still opt for the more costly variant and the more sustainable one. Somehow it would work.
- Participant stated that it would be obvious that those systems (renewable) are more costly. But that there would be profit in the play. In other countries, those systems would be 30 % cheaper. With quite flimsy reasons, it is so expensive here because the government apparently requires so much administrative effort. But that would be nonsense. The real reason would actually be that the government provides funding subsidies, and retailers are happy to take advantage of them. It could be cheaper.
- Very positive. Participant would not opt for another gas system, as some acquaintances have done it. That just wouldn't make sense anymore. Participant stated to have the reserves (in terms of money).
- Participant said that the funding process works, but in the end, one still has to come up with a five-figure sum, somehow between 15,000 and 40,000 euros. So, for his/her own situation, participant thinks he/she could manage it, even finance it in an emergency. The participant can imagine it would be difficult for many older people, especially those who have paid off their homes traditionally, have a small pension, live rent-free, but don't have any money available for major investments. And there are quite a few people like that where he/she lives.
- It was just luck, that the money was available then.
- Participant stated that it would be too expensive for him/her as a homeowner, because it would just not make sense anymore. When the system needs to be replaced down the line, say, the photovoltaic panels or something similar, which obviously don't last forever, there would be again retrofitting costs. That investment would never pay off in one's lifetime.
- Participant stated to contact Daikin. Daikin would be the world's largest manufacturer of heat pumps, a Japanese company. Based on the data the participant has, the total cost, including installation, would come to around €15,000. With 50 percent funding, that brings his/her share down to €7,500. Participant said, that if one looked at the cost of a conventional gas heating system with a suitable hot water storage tank, it's probably around €5,000, maybe €6,000, or at most €7,000. So, in the participant's view, the price difference isn't that significant when looking ahead to the future.
- Participant said that he/she is idealistic enough to believe that (it is financially manageable). If the participant ever needed a new heating system, he/she would somehow manage to go for something renewable. Participant simply can't do otherwise. Participant could not

reconcile using fossil fuels with his/her conscience—only in a real financial emergency would he/she consider switching to a cheaper, fossil-fuel-based option.

When exploring the topic of finance, the discussion came also on the topic of subsidies and how participants feel about that. The answers to this are shown in the following list of statements. These statements show that some homeowners did not inform themselves, others have problems understanding subsidies or are not satisfied with them. On the other hand, some participants mention being satisfied with how the subsidies worked out for them.

- Participant took all subsidies that were possible. That was very good in his/her point of view.
- Participant stated to have done quite a bit of research on how it works and how to go about it—partly because the participant is currently carrying out another energy renovation and is navigating all the available funding programs. The participant stated to have realized that it can get very complex, especially if one doesn't have someone experienced guiding one through it, or if one doesn't take the time and effort to thoroughly work through the various funding programs and figure out how to combine them effectively. Participant stated that it is not easy.
- The participant is not satisfied because a specific system would not get subsidies.
- The participant did apply for funding back then. Said he/she installed a photovoltaic and that at that time the funding pot was already empty. The participant stated to just happen to be unlucky and missed out on the subsidies. The participant stated being worried that something similar might happen again with a heat pump.
- The participant said that subsidies were part of the whole investment plan—making sure he/she could take advantage of available funding opportunities. He/she stated receiving superb support from the installer. The installer took care of the entire process, including all the aspects related to the energy consultant. Everything went through the company. So, to put it simply, it was a complete, hassle-free, one-stop solution.
- Participant stated it would be a pity that the heating system wasn't older. Then he/she would've gotten another 30 percent in funding.
- Participant said he/she is sure that if someone were a bit more diligent and put in extra effort, they might, let's say, reach around 20% funding. Participant said that even then, one is still talking about costs of around €15,000 to €16,000.
- The participant once investigated it with the investment bank and similar institutions but didn't find anything particularly substantial. Participant stated that there are possibilities, but that he/she got the feeling it could be more. To make it more appealing and accessible to the public, so to speak. The participant just doesn't feel that the current funding options are good enough that everyone would be jumping for joy about them.
- The participant stated not being a big fan of these funding programs, because they would always involve an enormous administrative burden. And one frequently gets completely different information from different institutions. A family member ordered a system and would nearly be driven crazy as one agency referred the person to another one and everyone would have said they were not responsible. Participant said one would only get proper information after you've applied. But one can't even apply unless one already knows whether it's possible in the first place. It would just be a complete mess.
- Participant has not occupied him/herself with them and does not feel informed.

- Participant said he/she is well informed. He/She informed him/herself through the internet and companies.
- Participant did not occupy him/herself with subsidies (due to waiting for the heating grid decision).

5. Discussion

The results of the interview analysis reveal a highly complex picture among homeowners. Some already have a new heating system, either based on renewable energy or still reliant on fossil fuels. Among homeowners with fossil-based systems, the range of reasons for a potential change span from those who are already planning to switch, to those who are highly interested, to those who have no intention of changing their system.

The reasons for not wanting to change their heating system are equally diverse. On one hand, some homeowners do not wish to be bothered by the topic and prefer a simple, ready-made solution. On the other hand, others are interested in the topic but feel financially unable to make a change, overwhelmed by the amount of information available, or lack the confidence and capacity to engage in the decision-making process.

For most participants, climate friendliness does not seem to play a role when evaluating their current system. Most homeowners using fossil fuels reported being satisfied with their system. However, some acknowledged dissatisfaction with the emissions produced by their heating system, even if they did not explicitly link this to their overall satisfaction. This suggests that while homeowners are aware of the environmental impact of their systems, this aspect is not yet central to their daily experience. It seems more important that the system “does its job” reliably and efficiently. Yet, when directly asked about satisfaction with climate friendliness, most participants recognize the issue and the need for change. Only four participants using fossil fuels stated they were satisfied with the climate friendliness of their system.

Regarding motivations for a potential change, financial considerations were most mentioned in various forms, such as the potential increase in property value, upcoming CO₂ taxation, and the role of subsidies. The second most frequently mentioned reason was the desire to reduce fossil fuel use.

When evaluating possible alternatives, the pros and cons of each system revealed a wide range of concerns and expectations. It is particularly noticeable that heat pumps are associated with significant uncertainty among homeowners. These concerns include the system’s technical functioning, its dependence on electricity from the grid or from a personal photovoltaic system, and the perceived noise level.

Some aspects were mentioned across all categories. For example, the noise level of heat pumps was a recurring concern. While some participants were unsure how loud a system might be, others noted that newer models have become quieter. Some participants even described the noise as annoying or a potential health issue. Another consistently mentioned aspect was the source of electricity—whether it comes from the grid or from an individual photovoltaic system. Positive aspects included the system’s climate friendliness, the potential for future technological improvements, and the availability of subsidies.

For district heating grids, participants highlighted the convenience and comfort of having the system maintained by a third party. One participant noted that the question of climate friendliness and emissions reduction is resolved if connecting to the heating grid is possible as the homeowner does not have to find a solution. However, negative aspects included the long waiting times to determine whether a connection is possible, the lengthy process of connecting, and dependence on the supplier.

For pellet systems, many participants expressed uncertainty about wood as a renewable energy source. Some questioned whether wood should be considered a fossil fuel, given its carbon emissions during combustion, and thus whether it truly offers a sustainable alternative.

Across all three systems, a clear pattern emerges: significant uncertainty and a lack of reliable, accessible information are widespread among homeowners. This is especially evident for heat pumps, where noise levels remain a key concern. The lack of professional, trustworthy information is further confirmed in the section on information sources.

The findings highlight that access to clear, accurate information about different heating systems is a critical factor—not only for homeowners but also for heating installers. Financial feasibility is another key determinant. Subsidies play a crucial role in enabling the transition of the private heating sector. Participants emphasized that subsidies influence not only the initial decision to change but also the concrete choice of system. Uncertainty surrounding the political and regulatory process also plays a role.

It is important to note that these results are based on a qualitative interview study with a small, locally confined sample. Participants may share similar backgrounds, values, and levels of awareness about decarbonization. As such, the sample may be more informed and motivated than the general population of homeowners. Therefore, the findings may be subject to selection bias and may not fully represent the broader homeowner population.

6. References

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7. Appendix 1

Table with the interview manual in German

N	Leitfrage	Nachfrage(n)	Thema
1	Mit was für einem Heizsystem beheizen Sie aktuell ihr Haus?	Wie alt ist das System?	Status Quo, Zufriedenheit
2	Haben Sie eine Photovoltaik-Anlage oder Solarthermie?		
3	Sind Sie mit diesem zufrieden?	Ggf. nachfragen warum / warum nicht	
4	Sind Sie aktuell mit der Klimafreundlichkeit ihres Systems zufrieden?		
5	Haben Sie bereits darüber nachgedacht Ihr Heizsystem zu modernisieren?	Nein: Was wären Aspekte, die Sie über eine Modernisierung nachdenken lassen würde? Ja: Was hat Sie dazu bewogen?	Grund der Auseinandersetzung mit neuer Anlage
6	Mit welchen Heizsystemen haben Sie sich bisher beschäftigt? <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; width: fit-content; margin-left: 20px;">f) auch fragen, wenn bisher nicht mit neuem System beschäftigt</div>	Jedes System: a) Welche Nachteile sehen Sie in diesem System? b) Welche Vorteile sehen Sie bei diesem System? c) Haben Sie sich mit anderen über dieses System ausgetauscht? Gibt es weitere Quellen, die Sie nutzen oder genutzt haben, um sich über das System zu informieren? d) Gibt es Heizsysteme, welche Sie aus Klimaschutzgründen bevorzugen oder ausschließen würden? e) Weshalb haben Sie sich bisher gegen dieses System entschieden bzw. was hält sie aktuell davon ab? f) Bisher sind Heizsysteme, welche auf erneuerbaren Energien basieren in ihrer Anschaffung und Installation deutlich teurer als Gas- oder Ölheizungen. Wie stehen Sie vor diesem Hintergrund zu solchen erneuerbaren Heizsystemen? g) Fühlen Sie sich ausreichend über Fördermöglichkeiten für dieses System informiert? Was fehlt Ihnen? h) Wie empfinden Sie die Unterstützung der Politik? (bezogen auf Wärmeplanung, Fördermöglichkeiten, kommunale Wärmeplanung etc.)	Informationsgrad, persönliche Bewertung der Anlagen/Unterstützungen

N	Leitfrage	Nachfrage(n)	Thema
7	Angenommen in ihrem Stadtteil würde es die Möglichkeit geben, sich an ein Nah- oder Fernwärmenetz anschließen zu lassen. Wäre es für Sie denkbar sich an ein solches Netz anschließen zu lassen?	Lieber als eine Individuelle Lösung?	Wärmenetze
8	Was halten Sie generell von Wärmepumpen?	Begründung	
9	Haben Sie bereits Erfahrungen mit einer Energieberatung oder mit Heizungsinstallateuren gemacht?	a) Wie empfanden Sie die Beratung? b) Ziehen Sie die Empfohlenen Maßnahmen in Betracht?	Professionelle Beratung
10	Zögern Sie aktuell, eine individuelle Lösung in Angriff zu nehmen, weil Sie abwarten möchten, wie die kommunale Wärmeplanung für ihren Stadtteil aussieht?		Verzögerung durch kommunale Planungen
11	Haben Sie das Gefühl, Sie hätten gerne weitere Informationen, bevor Sie sich um eine Heizungsmodernisierung kümmern können? Was für Informationen wünschen Sie sich?	Von wem sollten diese Informationen idealerweise kommen?	Wahrgenommene Unterstützung
12	Nach Abschluss der kommunalen Wärmeplanung sollen die Heizsysteme bei einem Austausch mit mindestens 65% erneuerbaren Energiequellen versorgt werden. Haben Sie bereits darüber nachgedacht, wie Sie dies in einem solchen Fall umsetzen wollen?		
13	Haben Sie noch Aspekte, welche Ihnen im Zusammenhang mit Heizsystemen besonders wichtig sind, und Ihrer Meinung nach noch zur Sprache gebracht werden sollten?		